

A STUDY ON EFFECT OF JOB SATISFACTION TOWARDS ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR AMONG COLLEGE FACULTIES

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Abstract

The current study has investigated the relationship between Job Satisfaction and their effect on organizational citizenship behavior among college faculties. The data were collected from 189 respondents from different colleges in Tamil Nadu. Job Satisfaction is positively associated with all the dimensions of OCB by the faculties of the colleges. Therefore, it was suggested that colleges should facilitate the process leading to Job satisfaction, so that staffs are better engaged in additional role behavior resulting in improved single and organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, College Faculties, Tamil Nadu.

INTRODUCTION

There is a huge change in authoritative design, capacities, interaction and conduct of staffs by primary changes. It has been distinguished that there is a general decay of confidence in the association among the representatives as a result of authoritative arrangements and underlying changes. As per Shaw (1997), staff conviction is a significant period of serious changes occurring in an endeavor for its prosperity, and assists with building and keep a confiding in connection among supervisors and experts. Many investigations have asserted that absence of trust and resulting issues in a wide range of organizations. (Ferris and Travaglione, 2004). Specialists have examined various elements related with authoritative citizenship conduct (OCB) and job Satisfaction (JS) There is an absence of writing in the space of confidence in association and less consideration has been given to the relationship of Job Satisfaction (JS) its predecessors and its ramifications.

Once more, the writing doesn't given sufficient proof with regards to the degree to which these factors are instrumental in deciding JS, accordingly affecting the authoritative citizenship conduct of staff. This study is relied upon to investigate the information on JS and its association with hierarchical level factors and its effect on OCB in Indian social setting. So, job satisfaction is an important concept that is not only related to an individual but it is relevant for the society's well-being. Job satisfaction is one factor that will ensure class performance and productivity of Colleges.

The Faculties would get interested to teach their students effectively when they are satisfied with their jobs. Like India, other countries in the world are trying to improve their quality of education, so that it meets the demand of globalization.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The association between trust in an association and OCB has been dissected in various studies. Organ (1990) analyzed OCB and the shared trust that underlies social trade connections guarantees that OCB will be reflected over the long haul. Lester and Brower (2003) explored that representatives' view of their chiefs' confidence in them impacted their work execution and OCB. Discoveries of Tyler and Blader (2003) and Gould-Williams (2003) detailed that trust all the while impacts hierarchical citizenship practices. Just couple of studies have examined the effect of JS on different components of OCB in Indian associations, so it needs further investigation. Nonetheless, the job of confidence in the Asian setting with JS and aspects of correspondence as indicators and OCB as result remains unexamined.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is one of the most widely researched subject. Job satisfaction acts as a moderator for generating the relationship between working conditions and individual outcomes (Dorman and Zapf,2001). Ahmed, Raheem, and Jamal (2003) conducted a study on job satisfaction of 236 Faculties in colleges. It was observed that the female faculties are highly satisfied when compared to the male faculties. The faculties working in the government colleges showed higher satisfaction than the faculties working in the private colleges. Gupta and Sahu (2009) conducted a study on job satisfaction. It deals with the relationship of job satisfaction with the organizational stress and place of control on vocational faculties. The results revealed that there is no significant gender difference between organizational stress and place of control on vocational school faculties. Noll (2004) examined the factors which affect the job satisfaction of the faculties. It was observed that the motivation, faculties relationship with the administration and working environment were the factors that affect the job satisfaction of the faculties. Agarwal (2004) had done his study on job satisfaction of college faculties. The results obtained that the experienced and married faculties of government colleges are highly satisfied than the faculties of the private colleges. It also revealed that the age and the marital status have no relationship with job satisfaction. R. D. Sharma and Jeevan Jyoti (2006) conducted the survey among private and government school faculties in Jammu city and the sample contains 120 faculties. The study revealed the level of satisfaction among the faculties is not high and the private school faculties are highly satisfied when compared to government faculties. Muchhal and Satish (2010) conducted their study on job satisfaction of college faculties in Bagpat district. The study reveals that there exists significance between female and male faculties. Kumar and Bhatiya (2011) indicate Faculties satisfaction level and their attitude towards teaching is affected by the gender, marital status and their minimum qualification. John (2010), Mehta (2012), and Zilli (2012) conducted a survey regarding the teacher's job satisfaction to know whether the teacher's perception is affected by the type of organization. The result observed that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of faculties.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current review estimates the association between Job Satisfaction and their effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

Objectives of The Study

- To find out the mean score and Gender of the staffs and their job satisfaction.
- To find out the mean score and Gender of the staffs and their organizational citizenship behavior.
- To determine the difference between mean rank towards Job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior of staffs.
- To evaluate the risk and gain of staff's Job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior.

Hypothesis of The Study

The following hypotheses were formulated to examine the relationship between OCB and JS.

- **H0**- There is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and job satisfaction.
- **H0**- There is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and citizenship behavior.
- **H0** - There is no significant difference between mean ranks towards Job satisfaction.
- **H0** - there is no significant difference between mean ranks towards organizational citizenship behavior
- **H1**- There is a significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and job satisfaction.
- **H1**- There is a significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and organizational citizenship behavior.
- **H1**- There is a significant difference between mean ranks towards job satisfaction
- **H1**- There is a significant difference between mean ranks towards organizational citizenship behavior

Sample

This is an integral a part of research design. This study utilizes the two sorts of information that is, primary and secondary. The data was collected from 189 respondents from various colleges in Tamil Nadu through stratified random sampling. The information's were gathered through mail as well as directly. A sum of 250 survey were distributed, out of which 212 were returned. Out of these surveys, 23 must be dismissed on account of missing information and the general example size is 189. The normal age of the staffs was 25-40 years. The survey was completed

throughout a period of 1 month.

DATA AND ANALYSIS

A draft questionnaire was developed on the basis of comprehensive reviews. The questionnaire is classified into two types. Part 1 consists of question seeking information about staff characteristics which include age, educational qualifications, experience, cadre. The part 2 includes questions that aim at obtaining details such as organizational citizenship behavior and Job satisfaction. This survey is conducted by using five point Likert scale. The study employed statistical tool such as Anova, Friedman test, Neural network, Tree structure analysis and spss software to analyse the data.

ANOVA Test for Gender of the Faculties and Job Satisfaction

Hypothesis

- **Null hypothesis H0-** There is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and Job satisfaction.
- **Alternative hypothesis H1-** There is a significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and Job satisfaction.

Table 1: ANOVA Test for Gender of the Faculties and Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction variables	F- value	Significant Value	Result
academic issues	.764	.516	Not significant
authority's attitude	1.392	.247	Not significant
Interacting	1.850	.140	Not significant
Appreciative	1.566	.199	Not significant
communicate	.162	.922	Not significant
Parents' attitudes	.870	.458	Not significant
lack of opportunity	.663	.576	Not significant
opportunity for interaction	.067	.977	Not significant
involvement	.106	.957	Not significant
well-paying work	1.058	.368	Not significant
service conditions	1.001	.394	Not significant
salary offered	1.811	.147	Not significant
salary on schedule	.168	.918	Not significant
Matters	.358	.784	Not significant
Attention	.909	.438	Not significant

There is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and Job Satisfaction. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and Job Satisfaction. The main reason for this is that the gender of the faculties does not take any role in Job Satisfaction. Here, the faculties do not have any idea about Job Satisfaction irrespective of their gender.

ANOVA Test for Gender of the Faculties and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Hypothesis

- **Null hypothesis H0-** There is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and citizenship behavior.
- **Alternative hypothesis H1-** There is a significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and organizational citizenship behavior

Table 2: ANOVA Test for Gender of the Faculties and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational citizenship behavior	F- value	Significant Value	Result
Obey	1.494	.218	Not significant
Breaks	.436	.727	Not significant
conscientious	2.477	.063	Not significant
Honest	2.063	.107	Not significant
Attendance	4.391	.005	Not significant
Complaining	.270	.847	Not significant
Focus	.406	.749	Not significant
Fault	.226	.878	Not significant
Magnify	.800	.496	Not significant
Noise	2.959	.034	Not significant
Meetings	.502	.681	Not significant
Function	.186	.906	Not significant
Memos	.665	.575	Not significant
Abreast	.764	.516	Not significant
rights	1.392	.247	Not significant
Problems	1.850	.140	Not significant
Precaution	1.566	.199	Not significant
Lend	.162	.922	Not significant
Orient	.870	.458	Not significant
Constant	2.186	.091	Not significant
Volunteer	.231	.874	Not significant
Impact	.253	.859	Not significant
Absent	1.808	.147	Not significant
Around	.402	.751	Not significant

There is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and organizational citizenship behavior. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the faculties and organizational citizenship behavior. The main reason for this is that the gender of the faculties does not take any role in organizational citizenship behavior. Here, the faculties do not have any idea about organizational citizenship behavior irrespective of their gender.

Friedman Test for Significant Difference Between Mean Ranks of Gender of the Faculties and Job Satisfaction

Hypothesis

- **Null Hypothesis:** There is no significant difference between mean ranks towards Job Satisfaction
- **Alternative Hypothesis:** There is a significant difference between mean ranks towards Job Satisfaction

Table 3: Friedman Test for Significant Difference between Mean Ranks towards Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction variables	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Degree of Freedom	Asymp. Significant
academic issues	8.78	235.773	14	.000
authority's attitude	7.80			
Interacting	6.50			
Appreciative	8.58			
communicate	6.53			
Parents' attitudes	6.36			
lack of opportunity	8.29			
opportunity for interaction	7.58			
involvement	6.55			
well-paying work	6.87			
service conditions	9.24			
salary offered	9.31			
salary on schedule	8.94			
Matters	10.06			
Attention	8.62			

From the above table, it is found out that all the variables related to the Job Satisfaction of faculties had significant values less than 0.05 at 1 Per cent significance; thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

So, there is significant difference between mean ranks towards Job Satisfaction of faculties. Out of fifteen Job Satisfaction variables, “The employees are well- informed on matters important to them in this organization” has the highest rank (10.06). So, the faculties opinion towards Job Satisfaction is influenced by well informed on organization matters that is important to the faculties. So, the faculties have Satisfaction on their job.

Friedman Test for Significant Difference Between Mean Ranks of Gender of the Faculties and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Hypothesis

- **Null Hypothesis:** there is no significant difference between mean ranks towards organizational citizenship behavior
- **Alternative Hypothesis:** There is a significant difference between mean ranks towards organizational citizenship behavior

Table 4: Friedman Test for Significant Difference between Mean Ranks towards Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational citizenship behavior variables	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Degree of Freedom	Asymp. Significant
Obey	18.94	1740.657	23	.000
Breaks	15.60			
conscientious	11.92			
Honest	9.75			
Attendance	8.58			
Complaining	12.04			
Focus	15.60			
Fault	15.82			
Magnify	14.45			
Noise	15.13			
Meetings	16.12			
Function	15.63			
Memos	13.38			
Abreast	16.58			
rights	15.54			
Problems	13.71			
Precaution	16.63			
Lend	13.28			
Orient	13.06			
Constant	6.02			
Volunteer	4.89			
Impact	5.41			
Absent	6.51			
Around	5.40			

From the above table, it is found out that all the variables related to the organizational citizenship behavior of faculties had significant values less than 0.05 at 1 Per cent significance; thus the null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is significant difference between mean ranks towards organizational citizenship behavior of faculties. Out of twenty-four organizational citizenship behavior of faculties variables, “I take precautionary steps to prevent problems with other workers.” has the highest rank (16.63). So, organizational citizenship behavior opinion towards faculties is influenced by preventing problems among faculties. Main reason for this is that the preventing problems among faculties reach at large extent.

Tree Structured Analysis for Job Satisfaction of Faculties

Table 5: Model Summary of Job Satisfaction of Faculties

Specifications	Growing Method	CHAID
	Dependent Variable	OCC1
	Independent Variables	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15
	Validation	None
	Maximum Tree Depth	3
	Minimum Cases in Parent Node	100

	Minimum Cases in Child Node	50
Results	Independent Variables Included	C4
	Number of Nodes	4
	Number of Terminal Nodes	3
	Depth	1

Table 6: Risk of The Model for Job Satisfaction of Faculties

Risk	
Estimate	Std. Error
.604	.071
Growing Method: CHAID	
Dependent Variable: OCC1	

Table 7: Gain Summary for Nodes for Job Satisfaction of Faculties

Gain Summary for Nodes			
Node	N	Percent	Mean
3	55	29.1%	4.56
2	77	40.7%	4.10
1	57	30.2%	3.21
Growing Method: CHAID			
Dependent Variable: OCC1			

Chart 1: Tree Diagram for The Job Satisfaction of Faculties

From the tree analysis model summary, it is clear that the Job Satisfaction occurs in organizations is important independent variables. This variable is contributing more towards Job Satisfaction of faculties. Indeed, Job Satisfaction occurs in organization is important independent variables that have created adequate towards organizational citizenship behavior.

CONCLUSION

The study is endeavored to make both the hypothetical and functional commitment to the current writing. To begin with, it expands how we might interpret Job satisfaction in Indian associations. The review ascertains the effect of job satisfaction held by the representatives and correspondence rehearses on OCB. In this business environment where workers' extra-role behavior is valued as it adds additional effectiveness to organizational performance, this shows the importance of JS in influencing all the variables of OCB. The component of the indicator variable goes on to firmly influence JS and OCB permits specialists to make a proper move to add the HR rehearses and hierarchical plan. Thus, the study concludes that organisational citizenship behaviour in enhancing job satisfaction is very important. All efforts should be taken to improve the job satisfaction of faculties. Having inferred from this study that freedom at workplace is the most sought after characteristic of job satisfaction, organization should create self-motivated teams at colleges. Some suggestions towards achieving job satisfaction are self-developmental opportunities, short term courses, seminars, workshops, high appreciation and rewards for commendable work are some of the ways in which job satisfaction can be improved. In this way with these discoveries, the administration can change its arrangements and framework to accomplish the ideal outcomes. Comprehension of this idea would be extraordinarily features through subjective as well as quantitative information. One more limit of this study was the absence of generalizability. The discoveries of this study can't be reached out to a wide range of administration and assembling associations, as just programming, media transmission and steel-fabricating organizations were remembered for the example, while it is conceivable that the discoveries might possibly remain constant in other assembling or administration associations. In this way, future examination can remember associations for different assistance and assembling exercises to expand the generalizability of the discoveries.

References

- 1) Babbie, E. (2001). *The practice of social research*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
- 2) Baron, R. (1987). *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 55(6), 154–187.
- 3) Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange the power in social life*. New York, NY: Bowen, D., & Lawler, E. III (1996). *Sloan Management Review*, 44(8), 65–99.
- 4) Kalleberg, A. L. (1977). *Work values and job rewards: A theory of job satisfaction*. *American sociological review*, 124-143.
- 5) Mehta, S. (2012). *Job satisfaction among teachers*. *IUP Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 11(2), 54.
- 6) Chen, J. (2010). *Chinese middle school teacher job satisfaction and its relationships with teacher moving*. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 11(3), 263-272. .

- 6) Liu, Z., & Yang, J. (2009, December). A study on job satisfaction of hotel employees. In *Information Management, Innovation Management and Industrial Engineering, 2009 International Conference on* (Vol. 4, pp. 204-209). IEEE.
- 7) Hu, X., Kaplan, S., & Dalal, R. S. (2010). An examination of blue-versus white-collar workers' conceptualization of job satisfaction facets. *Journal of Vocational Behavior, 76*(2), 317- 325.
- 8) Ghosh, S. M. (2015). Job satisfaction among government and private school teachers of Ranchi. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology, 2*(2), 88-93. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Special Issue 2652*
- 9) Yezzi, J. A., & Lester, D. (2000). Job satisfaction in teachers. *Psychological reports, 87*(3), 776-776. [8]Mckee, J. G. (1991). Leadership styles of community college presidents and faculty job satisfaction. *Community/Junior College Quarterly of Research and Practice, 15*(1), 33-46. [9]Ghosh, S.
- 10) Brodt, S.E. & Whitener, E.M. (2004). The role of managerial trustworthy behavior and organization. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 88*(1), 333–356. Korsgaard, M.A., Schweiger, D.M., & Sapienza, H.J. (1985). Attachment and trust in decision making teams: *Academy of Management Journal, 39*(4), 78–100.
- 11) Koys, D.J. (2001). The effects of organizational citizenship behavior, and turn over on organizational effectiveness: *56*(6), 199–298. Kulhavy, R.W., & Schwartz, N.H. (1972). *Journal of Business Communication, 18*(2), 55–97.
- 12) Branyiczki, I., & Bakacsi, G. (1995). Person-based reward system: *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 18*(5), 295–387. Pillai, R., Williams, E.S., & Tan, J.J. (2001). Are the scales tipped in favor of distributive justice? *International Journal of Conflict Management, 19*(5), 393–452.
- 13) Mackenzie, S.B. (1998). A measure of organizational citizenship behavior.
- 14) Moorman, R.H., & Fetter, R. (1992). Transformational leader behaviors and their effects on followers. *Leadership Quarterly, 6*(7), 212–332.